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STANDARDIZATION AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF TRIPHALA CHURNA

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ABSTRACT

Standardization is an essential measurement for ensuring the quality control of the herbal drugs and to have a good coordination between the quality of raw materials, in process materials and the final products. The present paper reports the standardization of Triphala Churna which is mainly used for constipation, indigestion and other abdominal problems. Triphala is an ayurvedic herbal formulation containing three fruits (also known as three myrobalans) in equal proportions. The Churna have been standardized on the basis of various physicochemical parameters. The tests parameters were found to be satisfactory and within the standard limits. Triphala churna and can be used as reference standards for the quality control/ quality assurance study mostly on plant drugs for their primary healthcare needs. The results obtained may be considered as tools for assistance to the regulatory authorities, scientific organization and manufacturers for developing standard formulations of great efficacy.

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INTRODUCTION

The generation today has a great demand for plant derived products. These products are increasingly being sought out as medicinal products, nutraceuticals and cosmetics^[1]. In order to have a good coordination between the quality of raw materials, in process materials and the final products, it has become essential to develop reliable, specific and sensitive quality control methods using a combination of classical and modern instrumental method of analysis. Standardization is an essential measurement for ensuring the quality control of the herbal drugs^[2].

The standardization techniques must include all aspects that contribute to the quality of the herbal drugs, such as correct identity of the sample, organoleptic evaluation, pharmacognostic evaluation, volatile matter, quantitative evaluation (ash values, extractive values), phytochemical evaluation, test for the presence of xenobiotics, microbial load testing, toxicity testing, and biological activity. Amongst all the test listed the testing of phytochemical profile is highly important as it has a direct effect on the activity of the herbal drugs. The fingerprint profiles serve as guideline to the phytochemical profile of the drug in ensuring the quality, while quantification of the marker compound/s would serve as an additional parameter in assessing the quality of the sample^[3]

Triphala is an age old commonly used Ayurvedic powdered preparation in Indian systems of medicine. This well known formulation is made by combining *Terminalia chebula*, *Terminalia belerica* and *Embolica officinalis*, in equal proportions based on the observations of Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI). The formulation is prescribed in the first line treatment of many ailments and is used as laxative, detoxifying agent and rejuvenator.^[4] Triphala is ayurvedic herbal formulation containing the three fruits (also known as three myrobalans) in equal proportion. Triphala is used in form of powder (triphala churna), tablets and extract capsules. It is beneficial for constipation, losing weight (obesity), reducing belly fat, body cleanse, indigestion and other abdominal problem. The churnam is exclusively used in multiple drug formulations in Indian system of medicine. The main aim of this paper is to focus on the quality control parameters of herbal formulations available in the market. The objective of our work was to run various standardization tests to check the quality and purity of the formulation.

Figure no.1: Amala (*Embolica officinalis*) Figure no.2: Harad/Haritaki (*Terminalia chebula*).

Figure no.3: Baheda/Bibhitaki (*Terminalia belerica*).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of material:

A marketed Triphala Churna formulation was purchased from an authentic vendor of Indore. Marketed formulation was identified on the basis of standard

Triphala churna contains three myrobalans (fruit rind) in equal proportion by **weight** without seeds.

Table no.1:List of Ingredients and Quantity.

Ingredients	Quantity (By Weight)
Amla (Indian Gooseberry) – Emblica Officinalis dried fruit pulp powder	33.33%
Bibhitaki-Terminalia Bellirica dried fruit pulp powder	33.33%
Haritaki-Terminalia Chebula dried fruit pulp powder	33.33%

ORGANOLEPTIC EVALUATION:

Organoleptic evaluation refers to the evaluation of formulation by colour, odour, taste etc.

Table no. 2: Organoleptic Evaluation of Churna.

Parameters	Properties
Appearance	Powder
Colour	Brownish
Odour	Characteristic
Taste	Salty

PHYSICOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATIONS**Determination of Total Ash :**

2 gm of powder was accurately weighed in tared silica dish and heated on burner until ash free from carbon was obtained, cooled and weighed. Percentage of ash was calculated with reference to air dried sample.

Formula for Ash value: = $100/a \times (c-b)$ Where, a is initial weight of sample b is weight of empty crucible c is Weight of crucible along with ash

Acid insoluble ash

Total ash obtained from above process was boiled for 5 minutes in 25ml dil. hydrochloric acid. The solution was then filtered through ash less filter paper. The ash was dried and the percentage of acid insoluble ash was calculated with reference to air dried sample.^[5]

Water Soluble Ash

The ash was boiled with 25 ml of water. The insoluble matter was then collected in an ash less filter paper. It was washed with hot water, and ignited for 15 minutes at a temperature not exceeding 450°C. Subtract the weight of the insoluble matter from the weight of the ash; the difference in weight represents the water-soluble ash. The percentage of water soluble ash with reference to the air-dried drug was calculated.^[6]

Alcohol Soluble Extractive Value

4 gm of powder was accurately weighed and transfer it to a dry 250 ml conical flask. Fill a 100 ml graduated flask to the delivery mark with the solvent (90% alcohol).cork the flask and set aside for 24 hours. Filter the solution and transfer 25 ml of the filtrate to a weighed, thin porcelain dish, as used for the ash value determination. Evaporate to dryness on water bath. Calculate the % w/w of extractive with reference to the air dried drug.^[6]

Water Soluble Extractive Value

Steps are similar to those mention in the point 5, use chloroform water instead of alcohol

Loss on Drying

Loss on drying is the loss of mass expressed as percent w/w. About 10g of dug samples of each formulation was accurately weighed in a dried and tared flat weighing bottle and dried at 105 C for 5hrs. The percentage was calculated with reference to initial weight .

Bulk Density

The term bulk density refers to a measure used to describe the packing of particles or granules. The equation for determining bulk density (D), $D_b=M/V_b$. Where, M is the mass of the particles and V is the total volume of the packing. It is the ratio of given mass of powder and its bulk volume. It is determined by transferring an accurately weighed amount of powder sample to the graduated cylinder with the aid of a funnel. The initial volume was noted. The ratio of weight of the volume it occupied was calculated.

Bulk density=W/V0 g/ml Where, W = mass of the powder, V0 = untapped

Tapped Density

It is measured by transferring a known quantity (25g) of powder into a graduated cylinder and tapping it for a specific number of times. The initial volume was noted. The graduated cylinder was tapped continuously for a period of 10-15 min. The density can be determined as the ratio of mass of the powder to the tapped volume.

$$\text{Tapped volume} = W/V_f \text{ g/ml Where, } W = \text{mass of the powder, } V_f = \text{tapped volume}$$

Angle of Repose

The internal angle between the surface of the pile of powder and the horizontal surface is known as the angle of repose. The powder is passed through funnel fixed to a burette at a height of 4 cm. Powder or granulation was carefully poured through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touched the tip of the funnel. A graph paper is placed below the funnel on the table. The height and the radius of the pile were measured using the formula^[1,2]

$$\tan = H/R \text{ or } = \text{arc tan } H/R \text{ Where } H \text{ is the angle of repose, } R \text{ being the radius of the conical pile}$$

Hausner Ratio

The ratio of tapped density to the bulk density of the powder is called Hausner ratio. It is related to interparticle friction and as such can be used to predict the powder flow properties. Powders with low interparticle friction such as coarse spheres have a ratio of approximately 1.2, whereas more cohesive, less flow able powders such as flakes have a Hausner ratio greater than 1.6. The equation for measuring the Hausner ratio is:

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \text{Tapped density/bulk density}$$

Compressibility index

It is the propensity of the powder to be compressed. Based on the apparent bulk density and tapped density the percentage compressibility of the powder can be determined using the following formula.

$$\text{Compressibility index} = [(v_0 - v_f)/v_0] \times 100,$$

$$\text{Or } \% \text{ Compressibility} = [(\text{tapped density} - \text{bulk density}) / \text{tapped density}] \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Triphala Churna was tested for various organoleptic and physicochemical parameters. The powder was found to be smooth, brownish in color having characteristic odour, possessing salty taste. The physicochemical Quality tests for Triphala Churna were performed for moisture content, ash content, water soluble extractive, methanol soluble extractive, acid insoluble ash and water insoluble ash and were found to be within the standard limits. The total ash value was found to be 7.34%. The water soluble ash was found to be higher with 4.28% as compared to the acid insoluble ash value of 3.81%

To determine the better solvent for extraction of churna, the extraction was done using water, alcohol and acid using a specified method. The water soluble extractive value was found to be higher 2.70% than Alcohol soluble extractive value 2.66%. Acid insoluble ash value was found to be 3.20%, which shows that the components of churna are highly water soluble. The loss on drying was found to be minimum with 0.14%. Hence proving that the churna shows stability even on exposure to intense heat. The flowability of the formulation was found to be satisfactory which was ensured by undergoing various tests such as tapped density which was found to be 0.71 volume. The bulk density was found to be 0.57. The Angle of Repose was found to be 30.24 shows good flow property. Hausner ratio of 1.2 which is less than 1. And the Compressibility index of 9.7.

Thus the standardization of Triphala churna was performed successfully as all the tests parameters were found to be within the standard limits.

CONCLUSION

From the present investigation various standardization parameters such as physicochemical standards like total ash, acid insoluble ash, water & alcohol soluble extractive values, loss on drying, phytochemical analysis, flow properties and safety evaluation were carried out, it can be concluded that the formulation of Dabur Triphala Churna contains all good characters of an ideal Churna. From the all above value it can be indicated that the quality of dabur triphala churna is of good quality. The sample shows satisfactory results, but the efficacy of the products can only be judged by doing the pharmacological studies. The result of present study will also serve as reference monograph in the preparation of drug formulation. For testing more specifically about the quality of the formulations we can further test it through various sophisticated instruments like HPLC, Mass Spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy, which will give us a brief idea about the presence and quantity of all the chemical constituents present in the formulation.

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REFERENCES

1. Patel, P.M., Patel, N.M. & Goyal, R.K. Quality control of herbal products, *The Indian Pharmacist*, 5 (45), (2006), 26-30.
2. Kunle, F Oluyemisi, Egharevba, O Henry, Ahmadu & O Peter: Standardization of herbal Medicines- A review. *International Journal of fBiodiversity and Conservation*, 4 (3), (2012) 101-112.
3. Wani M.S. Herbal Medicine and its Standarization. *Pharma info*, 5(6), 2007, 1-6.
4. Mukherjee PK et al, Clinical Study of 'Triphala' – A Well Known Phytomedicine From India. *Iran. J. Pharm. & Therap*, 2005; 1: 51-54.
5. Siddiqui A, Hakim MA, Format for the pharmacopoeial analytical standards of compound formulation, wokshop on standardization of Unani drugs, (appendix), Central council for research in Unani medicine, New Delhi: 1995.
6. Mukerjee PK, Quality control of herbal drugs, Business horizons pharmaceutical publisher, New Delhi: 2002.
7. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India Part 1, V-II (First edition), V-I (First edition), Ministry of AYUSH, Govt of India. 2008.

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